

1 **Dominance of methane emission pathways differs between small ponds with**
2 **contrasting dissolved oxygen status as a consequence of the varying extent**
3 **of methane oxidation**

4 *Adam Bednarik* & Eva Darenova*

5 *Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech*
6 *Academy of Sciences, Belidla 986/4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic*

7 **Corresponding author: Adam Bednarik (bednarik.a@czechglobe.cz)*

8
9 **Abstract**

10 Lakes are one of the most important natural sources of methane (CH₄) emissions, with
11 disproportionately large contributions from small lakes. So far, the limited knowledge of the
12 ratio between CH₄ diffusion and ebullition from various lakes hinders the ability for detailed
13 upscaling of lake CH₄ emissions. We report one-year measurements of CH₄ diffusive and
14 ebullitive fluxes, together with the stable carbon isotopic composition of CH₄ ($\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$) from
15 three small temperate ponds (< 0.02 km²) with contrasting dissolved oxygen status. While CH₄
16 ebullition was a major pathway of CH₄ emissions from oxic ponds (77 ± 19% and 73 ± 20% of
17 total CH₄ fluxes), CH₄ diffusion prevailed in a suboxic pond (60 ± 28%). This shift in the
18 ebullition-to-diffusion ratio was due to different extents of CH₄ oxidation as supported by
19 isotopic mass balance. Despite the various processes involved in CH₄ fluxes between ponds, no
20 difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$ emitted from ponds was observed. Our results suggest that seasonality
21 and the oxygen status of small, shallow ponds should be considered when upscaling CH₄
22 emissions from these ecosystems.

23
24 **Keywords:** ebullition, methane diffusion, stable carbon isotopes, methane oxidation,
25 methanotrophy

26

27

28

29

30 **Introduction**

31 Lakes are an important part of the methane (CH₄) cycle, contributing 17% to global CH₄
32 emissions from natural ecosystems¹. Within that, very small lakes (< 0.01 km²) represent only
33 a minor part of the global lake area², but they have been recognised to emit disproportionately
34 large amounts of CH₄^{3,4}. From the open water areas of lakes, CH₄ is emitted into the atmosphere
35 either through diffusion across the air-water interface (diffusive flux) or through bubbles
36 emerging from the sediments (ebullition). Many recent studies show that dissolved CH₄
37 concentration and its diffusive fluxes from the water surface to the atmosphere tend to increase
38 with decreasing lake area^{3,5-8}. Accordingly, CH₄ emissions from the smallest lakes create the
39 biggest part of the total lake CH₄ emissions per total area of the lake size category⁴. The
40 important role of small lakes in the carbon cycle is explained by their typical characteristics,
41 such as a high perimeter-to-water volume ratio corresponding to a relatively large input of
42 terrestrial carbon (e.g. leaf litter), frequent mixing, high metabolism rates and faster warming
43 of the shallow water column, which together often create favourable conditions for CH₄
44 production^{3,9,10}.

45 However, the two main CH₄ emission pathways, CH₄ diffusion and ebullition, often differ in
46 their environmental drivers^{6,11}. Even though ebullition is the main CH₄ emission pathway from
47 lakes¹², it is still the least often measured component of CH₄ fluxes and measurements are
48 particularly sparse from very small lakes^{6,13}. This can lead to a strong underestimation of total
49 CH₄ emissions. The limited knowledge of the ratio between CH₄ diffusion and ebullition from
50 various lakes hinders the ability for detailed upscaling of lake CH₄ emissions¹². For example,
51 CH₄ ebullition does not show a clear pattern with lake size, as described for diffusive fluxes,
52 but is rather related to other parameters such as water depth, temperature or indicators of
53 ecosystem productivity (chlorophyll a, total phosphorus)¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Consequently, depending on the
54 characteristics of a particular lake, the ratio between diffusion and ebullition may differ within
55 the same lake across different habitats and time periods or between different lake types^{14,17-19}.

56 The specific components of the lake CH₄ budget, including CH₄ production and oxidation,
57 dissolved CH₄ concentration and its emissions, are essentially related to the distribution of
58 dissolved oxygen in lakes²⁰. Methane is mainly produced in anoxic lake habitats, whereas CH₄
59 consumption takes place under oxic conditions. These contradictory processes (CH₄ production
60 and oxidation) usually run in parallel. Depending on the CH₄ residence time, methanotrophs
61 can remove most of the CH₄ produced, effectively reducing diffusive CH₄ emissions²⁰⁻²³.
62 Changes in dissolved oxygen in lakes and their impact on CH₄-related processes are studied in

63 detail, mainly with respect to the effect of thermal stratification and the subsequent magnitude
64 of CH₄ fluxes during turnover periods (periods of rapid vertical mixing). Ebullition is typically
65 higher in the stratified phases due to the developed anoxic conditions in the bottom waters.
66 However, high CH₄ amounts from anoxic deep-water layers can be rapidly released via
67 diffusion at turnover periods, creating the majority of the CH₄ emitted from lakes^{24,25}.

68 However, there is a lack of studies on how the diffusion: ebullition ratio differs with the oxygen
69 status of shallow ponds, where dissolved oxygen can be rapidly depleted in the whole
70 ecosystem due to the intense respiration²⁶. Even less is known about the effect of the shift in
71 dominant CH₄ emission pathways on the resulting stable carbon isotopic composition of CH₄
72 ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$) emitted from these ecosystems. The $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ in water results from the combination
73 of different CH₄ production pathways, which produce CH₄ with different ¹³C/¹²C ratios, and the
74 activity of methanotrophs, which discriminate against the heavier stable carbon isotope, ¹³C,
75 during CH₄ oxidation²⁷. Consequently, detailed knowledge of the $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ values of CH₄
76 emitted from specific ecosystems provides an important basis for source partitioning in
77 atmospheric inversion models²⁸.

78 In this study, we report measurements of CH₄ diffusive and ebullitive fluxes together with the
79 stable carbon isotopic composition of CH₄ ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$) from three small ponds (< 0.02 km²)
80 with contrasting dissolved oxygen status over one year. Using the stable carbon isotopic mass
81 balance approach, we aimed to determine the relative extent of CH₄ oxidation in the ponds and
82 its potential impact on the shift in the ratio of CH₄ emission pathways.

83

84 **2. Material and Methods**

85 **2.1 Site description**

86 Measurements were carried out in three small and shallow temperate ponds (L1, L2, and L3)
87 located in a broadleaf floodplain forest. The forest is situated about 6 km north of the confluence
88 of Morava and Thaya rivers on an alluvial plain at 150 m a.s.l. The site is characterized by a
89 mean annual precipitation of 497 mm and a mean annual temperature of 9.7 °C²⁹. The studied
90 ponds had an area between 0.2 and 1.5 ha and a maximum estimated water depth of ~1 m. Given
91 the small area and water depth, together with minimal emergent vegetation cover, we follow
92 the recent functional definition for distinguishing lentic water bodies by Richardson et al.³⁰ and
93 use the term 'ponds' for lentic ecosystems in this study. The sampling period covered one year

94 from April 2022 to May 2023. Ponds were ice-covered in two periods for ~25 days in total
95 during the whole sampling period. Additionally, pond L2 was characterised by the presence of
96 duckweed (*Lemna sp.*) covering between 0% and 100% of the pond surface throughout the year,
97 while it was absent in ponds L1 and L3.

98

99 **2.2. Environmental parameters**

100 Measurements of environmental parameters, as well as dissolved CH₄ and CO₂ concentrations
101 and fluxes to the atmosphere, were synchronised during field campaigns at approximately 14-
102 day intervals between April 2022 and May 2023. Water temperature (°C), dissolved oxygen
103 (DO, per cent saturation; mg l⁻¹), pH, and specific conductivity (μS cm⁻¹) were measured with
104 an environmental probe (Aqua Troll 400, In-Situ, USA). Additionally, water temperature was
105 measured in 1-hour intervals at each pond using temperature dataloggers (Minikin Tie, EMS,
106 CZ). The temperature datalogger in pond L2 was lost in the sediment, so temperatures were
107 modelled based on the difference in multiprobe measurements between the ponds during the
108 field sampling days. To characterise the water chemistry of the ponds, surface water was
109 collected five times during the year and analyzed for dissolved organic carbon (DOC),
110 ammonium (N-NH₄), nitrate (N-NO₃), and total phosphorus (TP). The maximum water depths
111 of ponds were qualitatively estimated by stick measurements from an inflatable boat throughout
112 the ponds. Sediment samples (0–10 cm depth) were collected in triplicates at each pond in
113 September 2021. The carbon and nitrogen contents of the sediments were quantified via a
114 CHNS-elemental analyzer (Flash 2000, Thermo Scientific, MA, USA). The characteristics of
115 the ponds are summarised in Table 1.

116

117 **2.3. CH₄ and CO₂ concentration in water**

118 The dissolved CH₄ and CO₂ concentrations in the water samples were measured in duplicates
119 using the headspace equilibration method³¹. The 60-ml gas-tight plastic syringe equipped with
120 a three-way Luer-lock valve was filled with 40 ml of water and 20 ml of hydrocarbon-free
121 ultrapure synthetic air (Messer Technogas, CZ). The syringe was shaken vigorously for two
122 minutes to equilibrate the water and air phases inside the syringe. Subsequently, the equilibrated
123 headspace was injected into a pre-evacuated 12 ml Exetainer glass vial (Labco International

124 Inc., UK) and stored at ambient air temperature until analysis within 24 hours. Approximately
125 17 ml of sample volume was used to create overpressure inside the vials.

126 The samples were analyzed using a cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) gas concentration
127 analyzer (Picarro GasScouter G4301, Picarro, CA, USA) by injecting 1 ml of a sample with a
128 gastight syringe (Hamilton, Switzerland) into a closed loop. The closed loop was created
129 between the gas inlet and the outlet of the analyzer for the manual injections of small samples
130 (for details, see Wilkinson et al.^{32,33}). The final dissolved CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations were
131 calculated from gas concentrations in the headspace, the volume of water, and temperature-
132 corrected gas-specific solubility of CO₂³⁴ and CH₄³⁵.

133

134 **2.4. CH₄ and CO₂ diffusive and ebullitive fluxes**

135 Diffusive CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes at the air-water interface were measured with a floating chamber
136 (volume: 3.3 l, surface area: 0.05 m²). The chamber was covered with aluminium tape to reduce
137 solar heating and it was equipped with a valve connected to a capillary tube (inner diameter 2.5
138 mm, 1 m long) at the top of the chamber to equalize the pressure inside the chamber after placing
139 it on the water surface. The chamber was connected to a portable GHG analyzer (Picarro
140 GasScouter G4301, Picarro, CA, USA) that recirculated the air (1 L min⁻¹) and recorded CH₄
141 and CO₂ concentrations in the chamber at a 1-Hz frequency. Diffusive fluxes were calculated
142 only from linear slopes ($R^2 > 0.9$) of the measured gas concentration over time (~3 min) to
143 exclude potential ebullition during the chamber deployment.

144 The CO₂ and CH₄ diffusive fluxes were calculated using Equation 1:

145

$$146 \quad F_D = \frac{\Delta C \times P \times V \times M}{A \times R \times T} \times 10^{-3} \times 86400 \quad (1)$$

147

148 F_D is the diffusive flux of CO₂ or CH₄ (mmol m⁻² d⁻¹), ΔC is the gas concentration change over
149 time (ppm s⁻¹), P is atmospheric pressure (atm; $P = 1$ atm), V is the total volume of the floating
150 chamber system (l), A is the surface area covered by the chamber (m²), R is the universal gas
151 constant (0.08206 L atm K⁻¹ mol⁻¹), T is the air temperature (K), 10^{-3} is the conversion factor
152 from mol to mmol, and the last constant is the conversion from seconds to days.

153

154 Ebullitive CH₄ emissions were measured with bubble traps (six traps per pond) consisting of
155 inverted plastic funnels (diameter: 33.8 cm; surface area: 0.09 m²) and floating material
156 (styrofoam). Bubble traps were deployed in the pond to cover multiple depths. The total volume

157 of gas accumulated in traps was periodically recorded at 14-day intervals. Traps were
158 completely filled with water at the start of each sampling period. A syringe with a three-way
159 stopcock was attached to the top of each funnel to enable sampling of trapped gas and refilling
160 i.e., resetting traps with water. Bubble traps were handled from an inflatable boat to avoid
161 disturbing the sediments around the traps.

162 The CH₄ and CO₂ content in bubbles was assessed from fresh bubbles collected manually using
163 a small bubble trap and by disturbing the sediments in the short transect at each pond on each
164 sampling occasion (every 14 days).

165 The gas samples of collected bubbles were transferred to pre-evacuated 12 ml glass vials (Labco
166 Ltd., UK) and analyzed for concentrations of CH₄ and CO₂ by injecting 20 µl of a sample into
167 the CRDS gas concentration analyzer as described above. The ebullitive fluxes were calculated
168 for each bubble trap using equation 2:

169

$$170 \quad F_E = \frac{C \times V}{A \times t \times R \times T} \times 10^{-3} \quad (2)$$

171

172 F_E is the ebullitive flux of CH₄ or CO₂ (mmol m⁻² d⁻¹), C is the average concentration of CH₄
173 or CO₂ (µl l⁻¹) in the fresh bubbles collected at the start and end of each 14-day sampling period,
174 V is the volume of accumulated gas (l), A is the funnel collecting area (m²), t is the decimal
175 number of days of the trap exposure, R is the universal gas constant (0.08206 L atm K⁻¹ mol⁻¹),
176 T is the temperature (K) of the gas sample before analysis, 10⁻³ is the conversion factor from
177 mol to mmol.

178

179 **2.5. Potential CH₄ oxidation in water**

180 The *in-situ* incubation experiments were conducted to estimate potential CH₄ oxidation in the
181 water in August 2022. A set of eight 50 ml glass vials was filled with water from each pond
182 (sampled 10 cm below the water surface), sealed with a butyl stopper, and crimped with an
183 aluminium cap. Two vials were immediately treated with 200 µl of 25% H₂SO₄ injected through
184 the butyl stopper to prevent further microbial activity^{36,37}. These two vials corresponded to the
185 initial water CH₄ concentration at the start of the incubation. The remaining vials were
186 incubated submerged in pond and incubation was stopped by adding 200 µl of 25% H₂SO₄ to
187 duplicate vials at three-time intervals in the range of 0–7 hours after the start of the incubation.
188 Water samples were analyzed for dissolved CH₄ concentration using the headspace
189 equilibration method. Potential water CH₄ oxidation was calculated from the linear slope ($R^2 >$

190 0.9) of the CH₄ concentration decrease over time and expressed as μmol CH₄ h⁻¹. Turnover
191 time was determined by dividing the relevant CH₄ concentration in water by its microbial
192 oxidation rate.

193

194 **2.6. Stable carbon isotopes analysis**

195 Subsamples for stable isotopic composition of CH₄ (δ¹³C-CH₄) analysis were taken from the
196 same vials that were previously measured for concentrations as described above. Gas samples
197 were analyzed in the laboratory using a cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) analyzer
198 (G2201-i, Picarro Inc, USA) equipped with a Small Sample Introduction Module (SSIM2,
199 Picarro Inc, USA) to determine δ¹³C-CH₄. Samples with high CH₄ concentration were diluted
200 using hydrocarbon-free ultrapure synthetic air (Messer Technogas, CZ) to stay within the
201 measurement guaranteed range of the analyzer and close to the concentration of standards used.
202 The calibration of δ¹³C-CH₄ was performed using certified isotopic standards (δ¹³C-CH₄ =
203 -68.6 ± 0.3‰, -45.5 ± 0.3‰, and -25.8 ± 0.3‰; Airgas, USA) and the measurements were
204 corrected for instrumental drift during the measurement time using the same standards. The
205 CH₄ isotopic data are reported in the standard delta notation (δ) expressed in ‰ relative to the
206 Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite standard.

207 The final δ¹³C-CH₄ emitted from the ponds to the atmosphere was derived from the CH₄
208 ebullition-to-diffusion ratio and the determined δ¹³C-CH₄ in bubbles and dissolved in water.
209 This took into account the stable carbon isotope fractionation for transport across the air-water
210 interface, with α = 1.002 based on a combination of kinetic isotopic fractionation measurements
211 of molecular diffusion conducted under laboratory and field conditions^{38,39}.

212

213 **2.7. Estimation of CH₄ Oxidation Using Isotopic Mass-Balance**

214 An isotopic mass-balance approach, based on stable isotopic discrimination during microbial
215 CH₄ consumption, was used to estimate the extent of CH₄ oxidation at the ecosystem scale.
216 This approach is widely used in many studies across different ecosystems^{21,22,40-42}. In principal,
217 the changes in δ¹³C-CH₄ in the water column relative to the δ¹³C-CH₄ produced in the pond
218 sediments associated with kinetic isotopic effect due to the preferential consumption of ¹²C
219 relative to ¹³C during CH₄ oxidation is used to estimate the fraction of CH₄ oxidized (f_{ox}).

220 Methane oxidation was estimated by Rayleigh fractionation model for a closed-systems⁴³:

221 $\ln(1 - f_{ox}) = [\ln(\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_source} + 1000) - \ln(\delta^{13}C-CH_4 + 1000)]/(\alpha - 1)$ (3)

222 where f_{ox} is the fraction of CH₄ oxidized, $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ is an isotopic signature of dissolved CH₄ in
 223 water, $\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_source}$ is an isotopic signature of CH₄ in bubbles produced in sediments, α is the
 224 isotopic fractionation factor for CH₄ oxidation.

225 The isotopic fractionation factor (α) associated with CH₄ oxidation was determined based on
 226 the changes in CH₄ concentrations and $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ during laboratory incubation of sediment
 227 samples. Approximately 5 g of wet sediment samples (duplicates from each pond) were
 228 transferred into 50 ml glass vials. Vials were crimp-sealed with butyl rubber stoppers and the
 229 aerobic headspace (ambient air) was enriched with CH₄. Initial CH₄ concentration was about
 230 6000 ppm with $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ -66.6‰ (i.e. close to natural $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ produced in ponds).
 231 Immediately following the CH₄ addition, subsamples of 0.1 ml from each vial were taken to
 232 determine the initial CH₄ concentration and $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$. Subsequently, duplicates from each
 233 pond were incubated at three different temperatures of 5, 15 and 25 °C (i.e. six sediment
 234 subsamples for each pond). The headspace of the vials was repeatedly sampled by withdrawing
 235 0.1 ml of gas with a gas-tight syringe (Hamilton, Switzerland) over 78 hours according to the
 236 rate of CH₄ oxidation. Samples were stored in a 12 ml Exetainer glass vial (Labco International
 237 Inc., UK) pre-flushed with synthetic air and later analyzed for CH₄ concentration and $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$
 238 as described above.

239 The α values were calculated using a simplified Rayleigh fractionation model for a closed
 240 system^{44,45}:

241 $\ln\left(\frac{CH_4}{CH_{4_initial}}\right) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \ln\left(\frac{1000+\delta^{13}C-CH_4}{1000+\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_initial}}\right)$ (4)

242 Where, CH₄ and $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ are the concentration and isotopic signature of the CH₄ in the
 243 headspace at subsequent time points, and CH_{4_initial} and $\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_initial}$ are the concentration and
 244 isotopic signature of the introduced CH₄ in the initial headspace,

245 The α was obtained by plotting Eq. (4) with $\ln(1000 + \delta^{13}C-CH_4)$ on the X axis and $\ln(CH_4)$ on
 246 the Y axis for a series of time points and performing a linear regression with a slope of
 247 $\alpha/(1 - \alpha)$ as described by Mahieu et al.⁴⁵.

248

249

250 **2.8. Data analyses**

251 The Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to test the normality of the data, and when data did not
252 conform to a normal distribution, a logarithmic transformation was applied. The homogeneity
253 of the variances was tested using the Brown-Forsythe test. If the data transformation was not
254 successful, we proceeded with non-parametric tests. The differences between the environmental
255 characteristics in different ponds were tested using the nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis ANOVA
256 followed by all pairwise multiple comparison procedures (Tukey test). All these tests and
257 analyses were conducted with a significance level of 0.05. Relationships between variables
258 were evaluated using the Spearman correlation. Analyses were performed and results were
259 visualized using software SigmaPlot version 14.0.

260 Considering that ebullition did not have a normal distribution, we used the median to express
261 the proportion between diffusion and ebullition on individual dates of measurement. To express
262 the temperature sensitivity of CH₄ ebullitive and diffusive emissions the Q₁₀ temperature
263 coefficient and the activation energy (E_A) were calculated. Q₁₀ value (the proportional change
264 in the flux per 10 °C change in temperature) was calculated following the calculation of
265 ecosystem-level Q₁₀ in DelSontro et al.⁴⁶. Thus, the slope (b) of a linear relationship between
266 multiple measurements of water temperature and the logarithm of the related fluxes was used
267 to estimate a Q₁₀ for CH₄ fluxes as $Q_{10} = 10^{10b}$. The activation energy (E_A) was calculated from
268 the Arrhenius type function as the slope of the linear regression of logarithmic (ln) CH₄
269 ebullition and the inverse of temperature (K) and multiplied by the universal gas constant.
270 Temperature values associated with CH₄ ebullition were obtained by averaging the hourly water
271 temperatures over each bubble collection period, while for CH₄ diffusion the average daily
272 temperature on the day of flux measurement was used.

273

274 **3. Results**

275 **3.1. Environmental characteristics, dissolved CH₄ and CO₂ concentration**

276 The ponds differed significantly in some of their environmental parameters (Table 1). The pond
277 L2 had significantly lower dissolved oxygen concentrations (DO) and pH compared to L1 and
278 L3. DO in L2 varied between 0.1 and 2.6 mg l⁻¹ from mid-May 2022 to mid-January 2023,
279 creating suboxic conditions for most of the year (Fig. 1a). By contrast, DO levels in L1 and L3
280 were never recorded below 3.6 mg l⁻¹.

281 In addition, pond L2 had the highest NH_4^+ , TP, and dissolved CH_4 and CO_2 concentrations.
 282 NH_4^+ and TP were significantly higher than in pond L3 only (K-W ANOVA, $p < 0.05$), whereas
 283 the dissolved CH_4 and CO_2 concentrations in L2 were significantly higher than in both other
 284 ponds (K-W ANOVA, $p < 0.001$). Dissolved CH_4 concentrations in L2 were even one to two
 285 orders of magnitude higher than in L1 and L3 for most of the year and showed no clear seasonal
 286 pattern, whereas in L1 and L3, they peaked in spring (Fig. 1b). Dissolved CO_2 showed a similar
 287 annual pattern across all ponds, reaching minimum values in spring (Fig. 1c).

288 The pond L3 had significantly higher NO_3^- concentration in water than the other two ponds (K-
 289 W ANOVA, $p < 0.01$), while L1 had the highest carbon and nitrogen content in sediments (K-
 290 W ANOVA, $p < 0.01$). The ponds showed no other significant differences in the remaining
 291 measured parameters (Table 1).

292

293 **Table 1:** Summary of individual ponds information, water and sediment characteristics (mean
 294 values and standard deviations).

Parameter/Pond	L1	L2	L3
Latitude	48.6810167N	48.6819800N	48.6849903N
Longitude	16.9519178E	16.9503086E	16.9552761E
Surface area (ha)	1.17	0.19	1.53
Maximum water depth (m)	0.94	1.01	1.06
Dissolved organic carbon (mg l^{-1})	22.1 ± 12.9	15.1 ± 1.1	8.9 ± 4.4
Nitrate (mg l^{-1})	0.6 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 1.5
Ammonium (mg l^{-1})	0.2 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 1.0	0.2 ± 0.1
Total phosphorus (mg l^{-1})	0.2 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.03
pH	8.0 ± 0.4	7.4 ± 0.3	8.0 ± 0.4
Dissolved oxygen (mg l^{-1})	8.1 ± 3.1	2.6 ± 3.3	8.5 ± 3.2
Dissolved oxygen (%)	77.0 ± 21.9	22.9 ± 28.0	80.7 ± 22.7
Specific conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	472.2 ± 81.8	475.0 ± 47.1	476.5 ± 81.5
Water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	12.4 ± 6.8	10.6 ± 5.9	12.8 ± 7.2
CO_2 concentration ($\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$)	98.3 ± 63.7	433.4 ± 256.4	93.7 ± 48.0
CH_4 concentration ($\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$)	1.7 ± 0.9	78.2 ± 80.5	1.8 ± 0.8
Sediment carbon content (%)	7.7 ± 2.6	4.5 ± 2.0	3.6 ± 0.5
Sediment nitrogen content (%)	0.7 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.3

295

296

297 **Figure 1:** Seasonal development of dissolved oxygen (a), dissolved methane (b) and carbon
 298 dioxide (c) concentrations in three ponds (L1, L2, and L3). Note the logarithmic scale on the y-
 299 axis of panel b -dissolved CH_4 concentration.

300

301

302

303

304

305 **3.2. Diffusive and ebullitive CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes**

306 Consistent with dissolved CH₄ and CO₂, annual diffusive CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes across the air-
307 water interface were significantly higher in L2 than in the other two ponds (K-W ANOVA, $p <$
308 0.001). The CH₄ diffusion to the atmosphere in L2 showed no clear seasonal pattern, whereas
309 in the oxic ponds L1 and L3 it peaked in spring (Fig. 2, Table 2). In contrast, the CO₂ diffusive
310 fluxes were lowest in the spring, when L1 and L3 were even CO₂ sinks, and reached their
311 maximum in the summer and early autumn (Fig. 2). Diffusive CH₄ fluxes in L1 and L3 were
312 positively correlated with water temperature ($r = 0.39\text{--}0.41$, $p < 0.01$; $Q_{10} = 1.5\text{--}1.7$), while no
313 significant correlation was confirmed in L2 ($p = 0.12$, Fig. S1), where diffusive CH₄ fluxes
314 showed a strong negative correlation with dissolved oxygen ($r = -0.69$, $p < 0.001$).

315 Bubbles released from pond sediments contained $1.2 \pm 1.3\%$ of CO₂, ranging from 0 to 5.2%
316 across all ponds. Therefore, the amount of CO₂ emitted via ebullition (annual mean $0.1 \pm$
317 $0.2 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) was negligible compared to its diffusive fluxes (annual mean 54.5 ± 54.5
318 $\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). However, bubbles became the sole CO₂ emission pathway during periods when
319 the diffusive CO₂ fluxes were negative and the ponds acted as sinks for CO₂.

320 Methane content in bubbles ranged from 40.3 to 97.4% with an overall mean of $70.9 \pm 12.2\%$
321 across all ponds. In more detail, it accounted for $71.1 \pm 9.8\%$, $76.8 \pm 12.8\%$, and $64.9 \pm 11.5\%$
322 for L1, L2, and L3, respectively. The significant difference was confirmed only between L2
323 and L3 (One-way ANOVA, $p < 0.001$). The CH₄ content in the bubbles was positively related
324 to temperature ($r = 0.30$, $p < 0.05$) in all ponds, with maximum values in September-October
325 and minimum values in January (Fig. S2). The CH₄ ebullition did not differ between the ponds
326 (K-W ANOVA, $p = 0.895$) and showed a strong seasonal pattern with the highest ebullition in
327 summer months in all ponds (Fig. 2). Consequently, three summer months accounted for 43–
328 63% of the annual CH₄ ebullitive emissions, while only 0.5–4% of CH₄ was released via
329 bubbles in winter (Table 2). Despite a similar seasonal pattern of bubble CH₄ content and CH₄
330 ebullition, bubble CH₄ content was significantly correlated with bubble fluxes (volume of
331 bubbles released) only in L3 ($r = 0.52$, $p < 0.05$). The CH₄ ebullition was strongly positively
332 correlated with water temperature in all ponds ($r = 0.63\text{--}0.89$, $p < 0.001$) (Table 3, Fig. S3).

333 Combined total CH₄ fluxes (diffusion + ebullition) revealed a clear distinction between pond
334 L2 and the other two ponds. Pond L2 had the highest total CH₄ fluxes (K-W ANOVA, $P <$
335 0.001), but the lowest proportion of ebullition (K-W ANOVA, $P < 0.001$). This suggests that
336 the total CH₄ flux in L2 was dominated by diffusive fluxes ($60 \pm 28\%$ of the total CH₄ fluxes),

337 whereas ebullition was the dominant CH₄ emission pathway in L1 and L3 (77 ± 19% and 73 ±
338 20%, respectively). The ebullition-to-diffusion ratio fluctuated throughout the year, exhibiting
339 the highest proportion of ebullition in summer (74–95%) and the lowest in winter (0–24%) (Fig.
340 3).

341
342 **Figure 2:** Seasonal development of methane ebullitive (a) and diffusive (b) fluxes and carbon
343 dioxide diffusive fluxes (c) from individual ponds (L1, L2, and L3). Note that the methane
344 diffusion for L2 in panel b is plotted on the right y-axis for clarity.

345

346 **Figure 3:** Relative contributions of diffusive and ebullitive fluxes to total CH₄ emissions from
 347 study ponds (from top to bottom: ponds L1, L2, and L3, respectively).

348 **Table 2:** Mean \pm SD ($\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) methane diffusion, ebullition and total fluxes (diffusion +
 349 ebullition) from individual ponds at each season and their percentage contribution to annual
 350 CH_4 emissions in brackets.

Pond/season*	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Year
<i>CH₄ diffusion</i>					
L1	1.5 \pm 0.9 (46)	0.8 \pm 0.5 (25)	0.6 \pm 0.5 (19)	0.3 \pm 0.2 (10)	0.9 \pm 0.7
L2	7.2 \pm 6.5 (16)	13.8 \pm 10.6 (31)	14.3 \pm 9.3 (32)	9.8 \pm 6.5 (22)	11.9 \pm 9.4
L3	1.5 \pm 0.8 (39)	1.2 \pm 0.9 (33)	0.6 \pm 0.4 (15)	0.5 \pm 0.4 (13)	0.9 \pm 0.8
<i>CH₄ ebullition</i>					
L1	5.4 \pm 2.6 (33)	6.9 \pm 3.3 (43)	3.3 \pm 3.0 (20)	0.7 \pm 0.7 (4)	4.5 \pm 3.5
L2	6.2 \pm 3.7 (25)	15.5 \pm 6.0 (63)	2.8 \pm 4.7 (11)	0.1 \pm 0.2 (1)	7.0 \pm 7.4
L3	5.6 \pm 4.6 (30)	8.8 \pm 4.9 (47)	3.6 \pm 4.1 (19)	0.6 \pm 0.9 (3)	5.0 \pm 5.0
<i>Total CH₄ fluxes (diff+ebul)</i>					
L1	7.4 \pm 1.9 (36)	8.8 \pm 1.2 (42)	3.8 \pm 3.0 (19)	0.7 \pm 0.5 (4)	5.7 \pm 3.5
L2	10.8 \pm 5.1 (18)	27.2 \pm 7.2 (44)	14.9 \pm 4.8 (24)	8.3 \pm 6.0 (14)	16.5 \pm 9.2
L3	6.8 \pm 2.1 (32)	9.6 \pm 1.8 (46)	3.8 \pm 3.4 (18)	0.8 \pm 0.4 (4)	5.5 \pm 4.0

* season is classified meteorologically (i.e. spring: 1st March - 31st May, etc.)

351

352 **Table 3:** Relationship between water temperature and methane emissions (n. s. = not
 353 significant).

Pond	CH ₄ emission pathway	Spearman correlation coefficient	P-value of correlation	Q ₁₀	Activation Energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Temperature range (°C)
L1	diffusion	0.39	0.001	1.5	30.2	4.8–25.6
	ebullition	0.63	<0.001	4.4	103.0	3.8–22.6
L2	diffusion	n. s.	0.12	1.8	42.0	3.5–21.0
	ebullition	0.89	<0.001			2.4–19.3
L3	diffusion	0.41	<0.001	1.7	36.9	3.6–25.9
	ebullition	0.69	<0.001	8.9	151.0	3.0–23.4

354 **Note.** The temperature coefficient Q₁₀ and the activation energy for L2 ebullition are not shown
 355 because they reached unreasonably high values due to the large number of zero ebullitive
 356 fluxes.

357

358 3.3. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 suggests various extent of CH_4 oxidation between ponds

359 The stable carbon isotopic composition of methane ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4) in bubbles ranged from -47.3 to
360 -74.5 ‰ throughout the year and did not differ significantly between ponds, with an overall
361 mean of 61.4 ± 5.2 ‰ (One-way ANOVA, $p = 0.49$). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 in bubbles was consistently
362 lower than the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 in water across all three ponds. However, the difference between the
363 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 in bubbles and water varied between ponds and throughout the year, suggesting
364 various involvement of CH_4 oxidation (Fig. 4). Indeed, a one-time *in situ* experiment confirmed
365 the difference in CH_4 oxidation activity in the water between ponds, with CH_4 oxidation rate of
366 0.21 and $0.12 \mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$ in L1 and L3, respectively (turnover time of 6.7 and 10.5 hours), while
367 there was no observed decrease in CH_4 concentration in vials incubated in L2 (Fig. S4).

368 To gain an overall understanding of the importance of CH_4 oxidation, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 values were
369 used to estimate the fraction of CH_4 oxidised based on isotopic mass balance. For this purpose,
370 we employed the experimentally derived fractionation factor for CH_4 oxidation (α_{MOx}), which
371 was obtained through the incubation of respective pond sediments. The α_{MOx} was found to be
372 1.017, 1.018 and 1.013 for L1, L2 and L3, respectively. The fraction of oxidized CH_4 strongly
373 varied throughout the year (Fig. 4) and was significantly lower in L2 ($28 \pm 27\%$) compared to
374 L1 ($68 \pm 16\%$) and L3 ($55 \pm 20\%$) (K-Wallis ANOVA, $p = <0.001$; Fig. S5). Consequently, L2
375 exhibited the lowest CH_4 oxidation, consistent with its highest dissolved CH_4 concentration and
376 CH_4 diffusive fluxes to the atmosphere.

377 Despite the different levels of CH_4 oxidation and ratio of CH_4 emission pathways, there was no
378 difference in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the emitted CH_4 between the ponds with an overall average of $-58.7 \pm$
379 5.6 ‰ (K-W ANOVA, $p = 0.915$, Fig. S6, Fig. 5). As a result, the stable carbon isotopic
380 composition of emitted CH_4 was very close to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CH_4 produced in the pond sediments
381 (61.4 ± 5.2 ‰), as derived from the bubbles.

382

383 **Figure 4:** Seasonal development of the stable carbon isotope composition of methane ($\delta^{13}\text{C-}$
 384 CH_4) in bubbles (red dots) and water (blue dots) together with the fraction of oxidized methane
 385 (black dots, right y-axis) for ponds L1 (a), L2 (b) and L3 (c).

386

387 **Figure 5:** Schematic overview showing the mean percentage contribution of diffusive (blue)
 388 and ebullitive (orange) fluxes to total methane (CH₄) emissions and the isotopic signature of
 389 emitted CH₄ ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$) in suboxic (left) and oxic (right) small, shallow ponds (DO = dissolved
 390 oxygen). The situation on the left corresponds to pond L2, while the situation on the right
 391 corresponds to ponds L1 and L3. Background graphic was AI-generated (ChatGPT- OpenAI).

392

393 4. Discussion

394 4.1. Changes in the relative extent of CH₄ diffusion and ebullition

395 Knowledge of seasonal CH₄ emissions rates and ebullition-to-diffusion ratio is essential for
 396 upscaling CH₄ fluxes from inland waters and their incorporation into the global CH₄ budget¹.
 397 In general, ebullition is considered to be the dominant pathway for CH₄ emissions from lakes¹².
 398 In line with this, we identified ebullition as a major CH₄ emission pathway from two of our
 399 ponds for most of the year. However, the lower importance of ebullition in one of our ponds
 400 and during winter in all three examined ponds suggests that the characteristics of the ponds or
 401 the environmental conditions can affect the resulting ratio between CH₄ emission pathways.

402 In terms of temporal changes, temperature is a crucial factor in the seasonal development of
403 ebullition due to the typically strong temperature dependence of CH₄ ebullition⁴⁷. As the
404 contribution of ebullition to total CH₄ fluxes usually increases with temperature in ponds,
405 maximums in summer and minimums in winter can be expected^{48–50}. Recently, Lv et al.⁴⁹
406 reported that the summer months accounted for 66% of annual CH₄ ebullition fluxes from
407 ponds, similarly to the range of 43–63% observed in this study. Additionally, the temperature
408 dependence of ebullition can be amplified by the nutrient status of the lake or the organic carbon
409 content of the sediments. These two factors were found to promote CH₄ ebullition rates
410 synergistically with temperature^{16,51}. By contrast, CH₄ diffusion across the air-water interface
411 generally exhibits lower temperature sensitivity than ebullition^{16,51,52}. Consequently, its relative
412 contribution to total CH₄ fluxes is higher during colder periods of the year. However,
413 investigations of both diffusion and ebullition throughout the year remain rare.

414 Consistent with the above-described patterns, we found that ebullition was highly correlated
415 with temperature, whereas diffusive CH₄ fluxes exhibited a lower temperature sensitivity. This
416 suggests that the seasonal development of the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio was primarily related
417 to the temperature sensitivity of CH₄ ebullition. However, the relative importance of ebullition
418 differed between ponds. Although the ebullition rate itself may vary between lakes and within
419 individual lakes depending on their characteristics^{14,48,52}, all three ponds in our study were in
420 close proximity, had similar sediment characteristics, and no significant difference in ebullition
421 rate was found between ponds. Consequently, the difference in the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio
422 between the lakes was due to the significantly higher diffusive fluxes in one of the studied lakes
423 (L2), which exhibited suboxic conditions for most of the year. The low oxygen content in L2
424 could be most likely related to the growth of duckweed, which reduces the amount of dissolved
425 oxygen by limiting the exchange of oxygen across the air-water interface and by adding labile
426 organic matter to the sediments^{53–55}.

427 Diffusive fluxes across the air-water interface are primarily dependent on dissolved CH₄
428 concentration and secondarily on factors influencing gas transfer velocity, such as temperature
429 and wind. We found two orders higher dissolved CH₄ in L2 compared to the other two ponds
430 in our study. In principle, there are two options why the concentration was higher - higher CH₄
431 production or lower CH₄ oxidation, possibly a combination of both. The very low level of
432 dissolved oxygen in L2 throughout most of the year could promote increased CH₄ production
433 due to prevailing anoxic conditions and inhibit aerobic methanotrophs due to a lack of electron
434 acceptors. In addition to the reduced level of dissolved oxygen, we also observed an increased

435 N-NH₄⁺ concentration in L2. Oxidation of ammonia can further reduce or inhibit the oxidation
436 of CH₄ by competing with the methane-oxidizing bacteria for oxygen or the key enzyme,
437 methane monooxygenase^{56,57}. In the case of higher CH₄ production, we could expect a higher
438 ebullition rate due to the close relationship between CH₄ production and ebullition. However,
439 such an increase in ebullition rate was not observed, suggesting that CH₄ production was likely
440 similar across all ponds. Instead, we demonstrated the absence of methanotrophy in the pond
441 water at L2 during the in-situ experiment, whereas oxidation activity was very high in the other
442 two ponds. While the oxidation experiment only provided time-limited information about
443 oxidation activity, the small difference in δ¹³C-CH₄ between the CH₄ produced in the sediments
444 and the CH₄ dissolved in the water in L2 suggests that CH₄ oxidation is limited in this pond for
445 most of the year. This is because microbial CH₄ oxidation is usually characterised by
446 considerable isotopic fractionation, resulting in a shift in δ¹³C of the residual CH₄²⁷. Indeed,
447 isotopic mass balance modelling showed that the extent of CH₄ oxidation in pond L2 was
448 substantially lower compared to the other two ponds across the whole year. Thus, high dissolved
449 CH₄ was most likely associated with low CH₄ oxidation rather than increased CH₄ production.
450 This subsequently led to high diffusion fluxes and a shift in the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio
451 towards predominant diffusion in suboxic pond L2. However, there were episodes, especially
452 in the spring, when the CH₄ oxidation was high, dissolved CH₄ was low, and ebullition
453 temporarily prevailed over diffusion fluxes in L2. This contrast might not be captured by short-
454 term measurements.

455 Differences in the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio for shallow lakes under contrasting states were
456 recently described between clear vegetated and turbid phytoplanktonic lakes, yet with varying
457 results. The CH₄ diffusive fluxes were dominant in turbid phytoplanktonic lakes, with no effect
458 of lake state on CH₄ ebullition, as reported for shallow eutrophic Pampean lakes¹⁹. In contrast,
459 higher ebullitive CH₄ emissions were observed in clear-water ponds compared to turbid-water
460 ponds, with no difference in diffusive fluxes between pond types, in Belgian shallow urban
461 ponds⁵². In our case, the most obvious difference between the ponds was the level of dissolved
462 oxygen. Similar variability in the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio, which was also related to
463 dissolved oxygen levels, has been observed in other ecosystems. For example, CH₄ fluxes from
464 agricultural ditches were found to be dominated by CH₄ diffusion, while they were strongly
465 negatively correlated to dissolved oxygen⁵⁸. Similarly, a negative relationship between
466 diffusive CH₄ fluxes and dissolved oxygen was reported from agricultural reservoirs as well as
467 from prairie pothole ponds^{59,60}. Naslund et al.⁶¹ reported CH₄ emissions from small reservoirs,

468 and only the reservoir where CH₄ diffusive fluxes exceeded the ebullition was characterised by
469 high dissolved CH₄ concentration, consistent with very low dissolved oxygen levels given by
470 high duckweed coverage. In addition, high coverage of free-floating plants can reduce the
471 ebullitive fluxes by trapping the rising bubbles⁵⁵.

472

473 **4.2. Resulting isotopic signature of emitted CH₄**

474 As the isotopic signatures of CH₄ emitted from specific ecosystems are important for source
475 partitioning in atmospheric inversion models, improving our understanding of the underlying
476 mechanisms that control the values of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ can help to improve modelling approaches and
477 reduce the uncertainty in emission estimates^{28,62}. The isotopic composition of emitted CH₄ is
478 determined by several factors, primarily the isotopic composition of the organic matter from
479 which it originates, the ratio of methanogenic pathways during its formation, and the degree of
480 isotopic fractionation during the transport process and CH₄ oxidation. The production of CH₄
481 in freshwater is mainly due to hydrogenotrophic (CO₂ reduction) and acetoclastic pathways,
482 which are characterised by different levels of stable carbon isotope fractionation that lead to
483 distinct $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of produced CH₄⁶³. Methane produced by the CO₂ reduction pathway typically
484 results in lower $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ ranging between -110‰ and -60‰ , while it ranges between -60‰
485 to -45‰ for CH₄ produced by the acetoclastic pathway^{27,64}. Therefore, the isotopic signature
486 of the CH₄ produced can be used to make a rough estimate of the dominance of a particular
487 pathway, but it has limitations due to the partial overlap of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$. The transport of CH₄ by
488 diffusion is usually associated with a slight shift in $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$, as the isotopic fractionation of
489 this process has been found to be substantially lower than that of CH₄ production or
490 oxidation^{38,39}. The CH₄ oxidation has a relatively large impact on $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$, with fractionation
491 factor α typically ranging from 1.004 to 1.030, while the actual fractionation further depends
492 on the composition of the microbial community, environmental conditions, and the extent of
493 CH₄ oxidation^{27,65,66}. The CH₄ oxidation fractionation factors of 1.013–1.018 determined in the
494 ponds in this study are within the previously reported range. Therefore, the $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ of residual
495 dissolved CH₄, which is subsequently emitted across the air-water interface, may differ
496 significantly from that of produced CH₄ due to microbial oxidation. By contrast, CH₄ released
497 directly from anoxic sediments via ebullition bypasses microbial oxidation at the sediment-
498 water interface or in the oxic water column, thus avoiding a shift in $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ ⁶⁷. Methane from
499 released bubbles is therefore often used to estimate the proportion of methanogenic pathways
500 or to calculate the extent of CH₄ oxidation, as it is considered to be unaffected by oxidation and

501 thus representative of the isotopic composition of the CH₄ produced^{21,40}. Consequently,
502 although CH₄ is produced in equal proportions by methanogenic pathways from the same
503 substrate, the resulting stable carbon isotopic composition of emitted CH₄ may differ depending
504 on the predominant emission pathway. However, studies linking the various CH₄ emission
505 pathways with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH₄ are still rare^{68,69}.

506 Given that we found a difference in the ebullition-to-diffusion ratio and also in the extent of
507 CH₄ oxidation in our ponds, it would be expected that the resulting isotopic composition of
508 emitted CH₄ would also differ between ponds. However, despite the assumption that CH₄
509 emitted across the air-water interface in a pond with prevailing diffusion would be enriched in
510 ¹³C due to oxidation, there was no difference in the isotopic signature of the emitted CH₄
511 between the ponds. In fact, the average $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the emitted CH₄, as determined by combining
512 diffusive and ebullitive fluxes, was very similar to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH₄ produced in ponds. This
513 suggests that the impact of microbial CH₄ oxidation on total CH₄ emissions was relatively
514 minor. The reasons for this limited impact appear to differ among the ponds. In pond L2, CH₄
515 oxidation was reduced due to suboxic conditions, whereas in oxic ponds L1 and L3, the
516 dominance of ebullitive emissions allowed CH₄ to bypass microbial oxidation in the water
517 column.

518

519 **5. Conclusions**

520 In light of the widespread decline in dissolved oxygen levels observed in temperate lakes⁷⁰,
521 understanding the impact of these changes on CH₄ emissions is crucial for more accurate
522 estimation of CH₄ emissions from standing waters. Based on annual measurements of CH₄
523 fluxes and their isotopic composition, we characterised the seasonal changes in emission
524 pathway ratios and CH₄ oxidation extent in three small, shallow ponds with contrasting oxygen
525 status. We found that the dissolved oxygen level determined the dominance of CH₄ emission
526 pathways, with diffusive fluxes playing a larger role in the suboxic pond due to the reduced
527 extent of CH₄ oxidation. As a result, total CH₄ emissions (diffusion + ebullition) were higher
528 in the suboxic pond compared to ponds with oxic water conditions. Interestingly, despite the
529 different levels of CH₄ oxidation and ratios of CH₄ emission pathways between ponds, we did
530 not identify any significant difference in the isotopic signature of the emitted CH₄, which was
531 only slightly enriched in ¹³C compared to the CH₄ produced in the ponds. This was likely
532 because the majority of CH₄ emissions were unaffected by the isotopic fractionation associated

533 with microbial CH₄ oxidation. In the oxic ponds, most of the CH₄ was released via ebullition,
534 thus bypassing oxidation. In the suboxic pond, the extent of CH₄ oxidation was too low to
535 significantly alter the isotopic signature of the CH₄ emitted via diffusion. Finally, the
536 substantially higher temperature dependence of CH₄ ebullition compared to diffusion
537 emphasises the importance of considering seasonality when extrapolating CH₄ emissions from
538 small ponds, especially in the case of ebullition.

539

540 **Acknowledgements**

541 The research was supported by Czech Science Foundation Grant No. 24-13457L, and by the
542 Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (grant AdAgriF - Advanced
543 methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest
544 landscape for climate change mitigation (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635)) and within the
545 CzeCOS program, grant number LM2023048.

546

547 **Author contributions**

548 Both authors designed the study and conducted the sampling. A.B. analysed the data, created a
549 visualisation, and wrote the first draft. Both authors contributed to revising the paper.

550

551 **Data availability statement**

552 Data and metadata are available in the Zenodo data repository at
553 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17867903>.

554

555 **Competing interests**

556 The authors declare no competing interests.

557

558 **References**

559 1. Saunois, M. *et al.* Global Methane Budget 2000–2020. *Earth Syst Sci Data* **17**, 1873–1958
560 (2025).

- 561 2. Verpoorter, C., Kutser, T., Seekell, D. A. & Tranvik, L. J. A global inventory of lakes
562 based on high-resolution satellite imagery. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **41**, 6396–6402 (2014).
- 563 3. Holgerson, M. A. & Raymond, P. A. Large contribution to inland water CO₂ and CH₄
564 emissions from very small ponds. *Nat. Geosci.* **9**, 222–226 (2016).
- 565 4. Rosentreter, J. A. *et al.* Half of global methane emissions come from highly variable
566 aquatic ecosystem sources. *Nat. Geosci.* **14**, 225–230 (2021).
- 567 5. Wik, M., Varner, R. K., Anthony, K. W., MacIntyre, S. & Bastviken, D. Climate-sensitive
568 northern lakes and ponds are critical components of methane release. *Nat. Geosci.* **9**, 99–
569 105 (2016).
- 570 6. Deemer, B. R. & Holgerson, M. A. Drivers of Methane Flux Differ Between Lakes and
571 Reservoirs, Complicating Global Upscaling Efforts. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **126**,
572 (2021).
- 573 7. Peacock, M. *et al.* Small artificial waterbodies are widespread and persistent emitters of
574 methane and carbon dioxide. *Glob. Change Biol.* **27**, 5109–5123 (2021).
- 575 8. Herrero Ortega, S., Romero González-Quijano, C., Casper, P., Singer, G. A. & Gessner, M.
576 O. Methane emissions from contrasting urban freshwaters: Rates, drivers, and a whole-city
577 footprint. *Glob. Change Biol.* **25**, 4234–4243 (2019).
- 578 9. Downing, J. A. Emerging global role of small lakes and ponds: little things mean a lot.
579 *Limnetica* **29**, 9–24 (2010).
- 580 10. Rabaey, J. S. *et al.* Freshwater Biogeochemical Hotspots: High Primary Production
581 and Ecosystem Respiration in Shallow Waterbodies. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **51**,
582 e2023GL106689 (2024).
- 583 11. McClure, R. P. *et al.* The Magnitude and Drivers of Methane Ebullition and Diffusion
584 Vary on a Longitudinal Gradient in a Small Freshwater Reservoir. *J. Geophys. Res.*
585 *Biogeosciences* **125**, e2019JG005205 (2020).

- 586 12. Johnson, M. S., Matthews, E., Du, J., Genovese, V. & Bastviken, D. Methane
587 Emission From Global Lakes: New Spatiotemporal Data and Observation-Driven
588 Modeling of Methane Dynamics Indicates Lower Emissions. *J. Geophys. Res.*
589 *Biogeosciences* **127**, e2022JG006793 (2022).
- 590 13. Sanches, L. F., Guenet, B., Marinho, C. C., Barros, N. & De Assis Esteves, F. Global
591 regulation of methane emission from natural lakes. *Sci. Rep.* **9**, 255 (2019).
- 592 14. Bastviken, D., Cole, J., Pace, M. & Tranvik, L. Methane emissions from lakes:
593 Dependence of lake characteristics, two regional assessments, and a global estimate. *Glob.*
594 *Biogeochem. Cycles* **18**, GB4009 (2004).
- 595 15. Vizza, C., Jones, S. E., Hart, J. A., West, W. E. & Lamberti, G. A. Pond methane
596 dynamics, from microbial communities to ecosystem budget, during summer in Alaska.
597 *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **67**, 450–467 (2022).
- 598 16. Xun, F. *et al.* Methane ebullition fluxes and temperature sensitivity in a shallow lake.
599 *Sci. Total Environ.* **912**, 169589 (2024).
- 600 17. Wik, M., Crill, P. M., Varner, R. K. & Bastviken, D. Multiyear measurements of
601 ebullitive methane flux from three subarctic lakes. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **118**,
602 1307–1321 (2013).
- 603 18. Wik, M., Thornton, B. F., Bastviken, D., Uhlbäck, J. & Crill, P. M. Biased sampling of
604 methane release from northern lakes: A problem for extrapolation. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **43**,
605 1256–1262 (2016).
- 606 19. Baliña, S., Sánchez, M. L., Izaguirre, I. & Del Giorgio, P. A. Shallow lakes under
607 alternative states differ in the dominant greenhouse gas emission pathways. *Limnol.*
608 *Oceanogr.* **68**, 1–13 (2023).

- 609 20. Bastviken, D., Cole, J. J., Pace, M. L. & Van de Bogert, M. C. Fates of methane from
610 different lake habitats: Connecting whole-lake budgets and CH₄ emissions. *J. Geophys.*
611 *Res. Biogeosciences* **113**, G02024 (2008).
- 612 21. Barbosa, P. M. *et al.* High rates of methane oxidation in an Amazon floodplain lake.
613 *Biogeochemistry* **137**, 351–365 (2018).
- 614 22. Thottathil, S. D., Reis, P. C. J., del Giorgio, P. A. & Prairie, Y. T. The Extent and
615 Regulation of Summer Methane Oxidation in Northern Lakes. *J. Geophys. Res.*
616 *Biogeosciences* **123**, 3216–3230 (2018).
- 617 23. Pajala, G. *et al.* The Effects of Water Column Dissolved Oxygen Concentrations on
618 Lake Methane Emissions—Results From a Whole-Lake Oxygenation Experiment. *J.*
619 *Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **128**, e2022JG007185 (2023).
- 620 24. Encinas Fernández, J., Peeters, F. & Hofmann, H. Importance of the Autumn Overturn
621 and Anoxic Conditions in the Hypolimnion for the Annual Methane Emissions from a
622 Temperate Lake. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **48**, 7297–7304 (2014).
- 623 25. Davidson, T. A. *et al.* Temporary stratification promotes large greenhouse gas
624 emissions in a shallow eutrophic lake. *Biogeosciences* **21**, 93–107 (2024).
- 625 26. Baxa, M. *et al.* Dissolved oxygen deficits in a shallow eutrophic aquatic ecosystem
626 (fishpond) – Sediment oxygen demand and water column respiration alternately drive the
627 oxygen regime. *Sci. Total Environ.* **766**, 142647 (2021).
- 628 27. Whiticar, M. J. Carbon and hydrogen isotope systematics of bacterial formation and
629 oxidation of methane. *Chem. Geol.* **161**, 291–314 (1999).
- 630 28. Basu, S. *et al.* Estimating emissions of methane consistent with atmospheric
631 measurements of methane and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of methane. *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.* **22**, 15351–
632 15377 (2022).

- 633 29. Stojanović, M. *et al.* Disaggregation of canopy photosynthesis among tree species in a
634 mixed broadleaf forest. *Tree Physiol.* **44**, tpae064 (2024).
- 635 30. Richardson, D. C. *et al.* A functional definition to distinguish ponds from lakes and
636 wetlands. *Sci. Rep.* **12**, 10472 (2022).
- 637 31. Magen, C. *et al.* A simple headspace equilibration method for measuring dissolved
638 methane. *Limnol. Oceanogr. Methods* **12**, 637–650 (2014).
- 639 32. Wilkinson, J., Bors, C., Burgis, F., Lorke, A. & Bodmer, P. Measuring CO₂ and CH₄
640 with a portable gas analyzer: Closed-loop operation, optimization and assessment. *PLOS*
641 *ONE* **13**, e0193973 (2018).
- 642 33. Wilkinson, J., Bors, C., Burgis, F., Lorke, A. & Bodmer, P. Correction: Measuring
643 CO₂ and CH₄ with a portable gas analyzer: Closed-loop operation, optimization and
644 assessment. *PLOS ONE* **14**, e0206080 (2019).
- 645 34. Weiss, R. F. Carbon dioxide in water and seawater: the solubility of a non-ideal gas.
646 *Mar. Chem.* **2**, 203–215 (1974).
- 647 35. Wiesenburg, D. A. & Guinasso, N. L. Equilibrium solubilities of methane, carbon
648 monoxide, and hydrogen in water and sea water. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **24**, 356–360 (1979).
- 649 36. Bussmann, I., Fedorova, I., Juhls, B., Overduin, P. P. & Winkel, M. Methane
650 dynamics in three different Siberian water bodies under winter and summer conditions.
651 *Biogeosciences* **18**, 2047–2061 (2021).
- 652 37. Matoušů, A. *et al.* Methane dynamics in a large river: a case study of the Elbe River.
653 *Aquat. Sci.* **81**, 12 (2019).
- 654 38. Knox, M., Quay, P. D. & Wilbur, D. Kinetic isotopic fractionation during air-water
655 gas transfer of O₂, N₂, CH₄, and H₂. *J. Geophys. Res.* **97**, 20335 (1992).

- 656 39. Happell, J. D., Chanton, J. P. & Showers, W. J. Methane transfer across the water-air
657 interface in stagnant wooded swamps of Florida: Evaluation of mass-transfer coefficients
658 and isotropic fractionation. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **40**, 290–298 (1995).
- 659 40. Borges, A. V. *et al.* Variations in dissolved greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) in the
660 Congo River network overwhelmingly driven by fluvial-wetland connectivity.
661 *Biogeosciences* **16**, 3801–3834 (2019).
- 662 41. Chanton, J. P., Powelson, D. K., Abichou, T. & Hater, G. Improved Field Methods to
663 Quantify Methane Oxidation in Landfill Cover Materials Using Stable Carbon Isotopes.
664 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **42**, 665–670 (2008).
- 665 42. Taillardat, P. *et al.* Carbon Dioxide and Methane Dynamics in a Peatland Headwater
666 Stream: Origins, Processes and Implications. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **127**,
667 e2022JG006855 (2022).
- 668 43. Liptay, K., Chanton, J., Czepiel, P. & Mosher, B. Use of stable isotopes to determine
669 methane oxidation in landfill cover soils. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* **103**, 8243–8250
670 (1998).
- 671 44. Mariotti, A. *et al.* Experimental determination of nitrogen kinetic isotope
672 fractionation: Some principles; illustration for the denitrification and nitrification
673 processes. *Plant Soil* **62**, 413–430 (1981).
- 674 45. Mahieu, K., Visscher, A. D., Vanrolleghem, P. A. & Cleemput, O. V. Carbon and
675 hydrogen isotope fractionation by microbial methane oxidation: Improved determination.
676 *Waste Manag.* **26**, 389–398 (2006).
- 677 46. DelSontro, T., Boutet, L., St-Pierre, A., del Giorgio, P. A. & Prairie, Y. T. Methane
678 ebullition and diffusion from northern ponds and lakes regulated by the interaction between
679 temperature and system productivity: Productivity regulates methane lake flux. *Limnol.*
680 *Oceanogr.* **61**, S62–S77 (2016).

- 681 47. Aben, R. C. H. *et al.* Cross continental increase in methane ebullition under climate
682 change. *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 1682 (2017).
- 683 48. Praetzel, L. S. E., Schmiedeskamp, M. & Knorr, K. Temperature and sediment
684 properties drive spatiotemporal variability of methane ebullition in a small and shallow
685 temperate lake. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **66**, 2598–2610 (2021).
- 686 49. Lv, M., Huang, P., Gao, X., Chen, J. & Wu, S. Intensifying methane emissions in
687 Chinese Ponds: The interplay of warming, eutrophication, and depth changes. *Water Res.*
688 **281**, 123576 (2025).
- 689 50. Xiong, R. *et al.* Warming effects on the emission pathways of N₂O and CH₄ and the
690 role of water column in shallow eutrophic lakes. *Sci. Total Environ.* **966**, 178705 (2025).
- 691 51. Davidson, T. A. *et al.* Synergy between nutrients and warming enhances methane
692 ebullition from experimental lakes. *Nat. Clim. Change* **8**, 156–160 (2018).
- 693 52. Bauduin, T., Gypens, N. & Borges, A. V. Methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide
694 emissions from two clear-water and two turbid-water urban ponds in Brussels (Belgium).
695 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-1315> (2024).
- 696 53. Rabaey, J. & Cotner, J. Pond greenhouse gas emissions controlled by duckweed
697 coverage. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **10**, 889289 (2022).
- 698 54. Morris, P. F. & Barker, W. G. Oxygen transport rates through mats of *Lemna minor*
699 and *Wolffia* sp. and oxygen tension within and below the mat. *Can. J. Bot.* **55**, 1926–1932
700 (1977).
- 701 55. Kosten, S. *et al.* Fate of methane in aquatic systems dominated by free-floating plants.
702 *Water Res.* **104**, 200–207 (2016).
- 703 56. Bosse, U., Frenzel, P. & Conrad, R. Inhibition of methane oxidation by ammonium in
704 the surface layer of a littoral sediment. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **13**, 123–134 (1993).

- 705 57. Bodelier, P. L. Interactions between nitrogenous fertilizers and methane cycling in
706 wetland and upland soils. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* **3**, 379–388 (2011).
- 707 58. Niu, X. *et al.* Quantifying the contribution of methane diffusion and ebullition from
708 agricultural ditches. *Sci. Total Environ.* **919**, 170912 (2024).
- 709 59. Jensen, S. A. *et al.* Seasonal variability of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O content and fluxes in
710 small agricultural reservoirs of the northern Great Plains. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **10**, 895531
711 (2022).
- 712 60. Miranda, L. T. & Whitfield, C. J. The Role of Multiple Greenhouse Gas Flux
713 Pathways at Four Prairie Pothole Ponds. *Wetlands* **44**, 123 (2024).
- 714 61. Naslund, L. C., Mehring, A. S., Rosemond, A. D. & Wenger, S. J. Toward more
715 accurate estimates of carbon emissions from small reservoirs. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **69**, 1350–
716 1364 (2024).
- 717 62. Kuhn, M. A. *et al.* Controls on Stable Methane Isotope Values in Northern Peatlands
718 and Potential Shifts in Values Under Permafrost Thaw Scenarios. *J. Geophys. Res.*
719 *Biogeosciences* **129**, e2023JG007837 (2024).
- 720 63. Conrad, R. Quantification of methanogenic pathways using stable carbon isotopic
721 signatures: a review and a proposal. *Org. Geochem.* **36**, 739–752 (2005).
- 722 64. Conrad, R., Claus, P. & Casper, P. Characterization of stable isotope fractionation
723 during methane production in the sediment of a eutrophic lake, Lake Dagow, Germany.
724 *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **54**, 457–471 (2009).
- 725 65. Bastviken, D., Ejlertsson, J. & Tranvik, L. Measurement of Methane Oxidation in
726 Lakes: A Comparison of Methods. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **36**, 3354–3361 (2002).
- 727 66. Chanton, J. P., Powelson, D. K., Abichou, T., Fields, D. & Green, R. Effect of
728 Temperature and Oxidation Rate on Carbon-isotope Fractionation during Methane
729 Oxidation by Landfill Cover Materials. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **42**, 7818–7823 (2008).

- 730 67. Chanton, J. P. The effect of gas transport on the isotope signature of methane in
731 wetlands. *Org. Geochem.* **36**, 753–768 (2005).
- 732 68. Thottathil, S. D. & Prairie, Y. T. Coupling of stable carbon isotopic signature of
733 methane and ebullitive fluxes in northern temperate lakes. *Sci. Total Environ.* **777**, 146117
734 (2021).
- 735 69. Robison, A. L. *et al.* Dominance of Diffusive Methane Emissions From Lowland
736 Headwater Streams Promotes Oxidation and Isotopic Enrichment. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **9**,
737 791305 (2022).
- 738 70. Jane, S. F. *et al.* Widespread deoxygenation of temperate lakes. *Nature* **594**, 66–70
739 (2021).
- 740

Supplementary information for

Dominance of methane emission pathways differs between small ponds with contrasting dissolved oxygen status as a consequence of the varying extent of methane oxidation

Adam Bednarik & Eva Darenova*

*Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences,
Belidla 4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic*

*Corresponding author: Adam Bednarik (bednarik.a@czechglobe.cz)

Fig. S1: Relationship between diffusive CH₄ fluxes and water temperature for individual ponds (L1, L2, and L3). Note that the CH₄ diffusion for L2 is plotted on the right y-axis for clarity (r = Spearman correlation coefficient, n.s. = not significant).

Fig. S2: Seasonal development of methane content in manually released bubbles (%) from individual ponds' sediments (L1, L2, and L3).

Fig. S3: Relationship between ebullitive CH₄ fluxes and water temperature for individual ponds L1, L2, and L3 (r = Spearman correlation coefficient).

Fig. S4: Time development data of incubation experiments for the determination of the potential CH_4 oxidation in water.

Fig. S5: The fraction of CH_4 oxidised in individual ponds based on stable carbon isotope mass balance. Statistically significant differences between the sites are marked by different letters.

Fig. S6: The comparison of the stable carbon isotopic composition of emitted CH₄ between ponds.